

POTENTIAL FOR TOURISM -STUDY OF FORTS IN NASIK DISTRICT

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Abstract

Tourism is a tertiary economic activity. It is growing fast and has great prosper. 'Tourism has been recognized as an important sector of global economy with a contribution of about 91 percent of domestic tourism' (Pankaj Bhalla, 2004). Tourism is an important activity who generate number of jobs and also infrastructural development in related region and also support to social, cultural as well as economic development in respective region. The growth speed of this tertiary economic activity is increasing day by day in world, because of high standard of living, economic development of the region, high purchasing power parity. Easy availability of transport facilities, good accession information of tourism places, online accommodation, best season and booking through electronic media are also support positively.

Some tourists places can highly contribute to socio-economic development of the region, if they developed. Best example is Durg Bhandar near Tryambakeshwar in Nasik district. Most of these forts are located over the hills amid picturesque natural beauty. These ancient and historical forts in Nasik district are the monuments of national importance and form exquisite tourist and trekking spots. These tourism places have much potential of tourism.

In this study we selected 7 forts out of 36. Main study has done on physical and social attributes. And find the Social as well as Physical attribute Potential value which are help to give suggestions for planner and developer for future planning which help to develop region. This study widely helps development of historical tourist places. Therefore, this study mainly focus on how to develop some forts as good tourist places which can help to develop the economic and social status of the people in the region and development of the region.

Key words: Tourism development, forts, social and physical attributes, potential values.

Study Region

Nashik District is located between 18.33 degree and 20.53 degree North latitude and between 73.16 degree and 75.16 degree East Longitude at Northwest part of the Maharashtra state, at 565 meters above mean sea level. The Godavari river originates from Trimbakeshwar in Nashik. One of the 12 Jyotirlingas also at Trimbakeshwar. Nashik, Malegaon, Manmad, Igatpuri are some of the big cities situated in the Nashik District. Nashik district is the third largest district in Maharashtra in terms of Population of 61,09,052 and area occupying an area of 15,582 km² in the north Maharashtra region. The Western Ghats or Sahyadri range stretches from north to south across the western portion of the district. With the exception of the westernmost few villages, the western portion is hilly, and intersected by ravines, and only the simplest kind of cultivation is possible. The western slope of the Ghats is drained by several rivers, including the Daman Ganga River, which drains westwards to the Arabian Sea.

Important of Study

The Sahyadri hills (Western Ghats) and the Deccan Plateau has highly support to develop Maratha Empire to King Shivaji in 17th Century. With the help of geographical feature and small armies he developed guerrilla warfare. King Shivaji fights with Bijapur dynasty of Adilshahi and Qutub Shahi Empire and Mughal Empire and established and develop Maratha Empire in very short period. Chhatrapati Shivaji Raje Bhonsle won numerous battles even with insignificant soldiers and arms with help of forts and guerrilla warfare agents numbers of enemy with huge arms and soldiers.

For protection and extinction of Maratha Empire King Shivaji Built numbers of forts in Sahyadri. Few forts are in Nasik district. The architecture, geographical location,

construction of forts, transportation, food security, drinking water, ammunition and commutation facilities have better in maximum forts. These forts are paramount important for Maratha history. That's why these forts should develop as heritage historical places which encourage for next generation. This study widely helps develop historical tourist places. It also helps to students, researcher and planner.

Objectives

The main objective of the study is to find out Tourism Potential of forts in study region.

The present research has been undertaken to make on in-depth and comprehensive study of historical Forts and other facilities related to tourism in Nasik district by evaluating following objectives:

- i) Examining the physical background of study region.
- ii) Studying availability general facilities.
- iii) Find out the social as well as physical attribute potential value
- iv) Suggesting remedial measures for better tourism development in study region.

Database and Methodology

The data of historical forts and other tourist places are collected through personal visit to places and interview. Some infrastructure data has been collected from PWD department. Some secondary data has been collected from books. Primary data has calculated for social and physical attributes potential values. For interpretation these value are shown by compound bar graph. For this study out of 36 forts 7 forts has selected on the basis of size, architecture and facilities on fort.

Discussion

Tourism is now rapidly developing industry worldwide. Its highly help to economic and social development of region. Now the economic condition, awareness about tourism, purchasing power of common people, accessibility, speedy and easily availability of transportation facility, easily getting knowledge about tourist places and electronic media have encourage to people to tourism. Nowadays tourism is developing very fast, but not in all areas. Some region has having high development and some are having low.

Some tourism places are also yet not very popular and develop because of the information of these places is not reaches to people or tourist in proper way. If these places can develop, they can highly contribute to socio economic development of the

region. Out of them some forts are historical importance, they rulers and stand gracefully as witnesses of significant historical events. Most of these forts are located over the hills amid picturesque natural beauty. The structure of the fort flaunts the brilliant architecture prevailing in the bygone eras. From defence as well as artistic point of view, the forts have an impressive structure. Some of the forts have been well preserved by the by forest department, some local bodies and Government of Maharashtra, while many have ruined owing to various battles and time. These ancient forts in Nasik district are the monuments of national importance and form exquisite tourist and trekking spots. Some social, environmental as well as physical factors have potential for development the tourism. In this study we mainly focus on social and physical attributes.

For this study we have select 120 questionnaires from tourists, trekkers, geographers and local people on social and physical attributes. Social and physical attribute are selected from opinion from people. Selected social aspects have been distributed in three parameter and physical aspects are distributed in six parameters. Table -1 shows the ranking of social and physical attribute. In social attribute people have gave first rank to annual tourist influx and third rank to local market. In physical attribute people gave first rank to physical accessibility, then accommodation, tourist information and guide and low rank to parking.

Table 1: Ranking For Social And Physical Attributes

Social Attributes	Rank 1	Rank 2	Rank 3	Total			
Annual Tourist Influx (S1)	67	32	21	120			
Average Duration Of stay (S2)	39	54	27	120			
Local market (S3)	36	39	45	120			
Physical Attributes	Rank 1	Rank 2	Rank 3	Rank 4	Rank 5	Rank6	Total
Physical Accessibility (P1)	34	22	16	20	12	16	120
Food and Water (P2)	21	19	18	28	22	12	120
Accommodation (P3)	30	36	28	10	8	8	120
Transport Facility (P4)	25	20	16	18	33	8	120
Parking (P5)	14	17	9	7	17	56	120
Tourist Information and Guide P(6)	29	28	30	14	10	9	120

On the basis of ranking of attribute we calculate weights. Table -2 elaborate the value of weights for selected social and physical attributes.

Table 2: Weights of Attribute

Attribute and Ranks		Weights
Social Attributes		
Rank 1 (S1)	Annual Tourist Influx	0.5 (3/6)*
Rank 2 (S2)	Average Duration Of stay	0.33 (2/6)
Rank 3 (S3)	Local market	0.17 (1/6)

*Cumulative rank value: $1+2+3=6$

Physical Attributes		
Rank 1 (P1)	Physical Accessibility	0.285 (6/21)*
Rank 2 (P2)	Food and Water	0.190 (4/21)
Rank 3 (P3)	Accommodation	0.095 (2/21)
Rank 1 (P4)	Transport Facility	0.238 (5/21)
Rank 2 (P5)	Parking	0.047 (1/21)
Rank 3 (P6)	Tourist Information and Guide	0.143 (3/21)

*Cumulative rank value: $1+2+3+4+5+6=21$

In study region selected tourist places having social and physical attributes with different quality and quantity. On the basis, quality and quantity, 5- points scaling of an individual attribute has been framed. 1 refers to poor or worst situation and 5 refers as the best situation of attribute. These values are converted in lowest value 1 is as 0.2 (1/5) and highest scale 5 is as 1 (5/5). This scaling shown with colour range with black to white has been applied from 1 to 5 respectively. On basis of Weights value and scaling value we calculate social and potential value of individual tourist place.

$$\text{Total Potential Value (Vt)} = 0.6 * \text{Potential Value in Social Aspect (Vs)} + 0.4 * \text{Potential Value in Physical Aspect (Vp)}$$

$$\text{Potential Value in Social Aspect (Vs)} = 0.5 * \text{Grade in Tourist Influx} + 0.33 * \text{Grade in Average Duration Of stay} + 0.17 * \text{Grade in Local market}$$

$$\text{Potential Value in Physical Aspect (Vp)} = 0.285 * \text{Grade in Physical Accessibility} + 0.190 * \text{Grade in Food and Water} + 0.095 * \text{Grade in Accommodation}$$

Guide	+ 0.238* Grade in Transport Facility + 0.047* Grade in Parking + 0.143* Grade in Tourist Information &
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Table 3: Interpretation of Scaling for a Sample Attribute

Attributes	1 (0.2)	2 (0.4)	3 (0.6)	4 (0.8)	5 (1.0)
	Poor	Average	Good	Better	Excellent

Table 4: Scaling for social and physical attribute. And calculating potential value

Spot (Fort)	S1	S2	S3	Vs	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	Vp
Harihar	1	0.6	0.4	0.766	1	0.8	0.8	0.6	0.8	0.8	0.808
Tringalgad	0.4	0.2	0.6	0.368	1	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.4	0.4	0.675
Ramsej	1	0.4	0.2	0.666	1	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.4	0.8	0.837
Anjaneri	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.6	0.2	0.218
Mulher	1	0.4	0.2	0.666	0.4	0.8	0.6	0.2	0.8	0.8	0.523
Bhaskargad	0.8	0.2	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.352
Alang	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.8	0.2	0.2	0.6	0.4	0.418

Social attribute potential values-

The table -4 elaborate the present quality and quantity of different attribute. The fort Tringalgad, Anjaneri, Alang shows value of Annual Tourist Influx is 0.4 is showing that reduce tourist influx. The fort Tringalgad, Anjaneri, Bhaskargad, Alang forts shows poor values in average duration of stay is 0.2. This figure says to develop the attraction of long stay in concern fort area. Except Tringalgad fort all remaining fort shows the value of local market is 0.4 and less. It means local market should be develop in respective area.

Physical attribute potential values-

In physical attribute, potential values of Physical Accessibility found less in Anjaneri, Mulher, Alang 0.2, 0.4 and 0.4 respectively. This reflect that there are not good facility to reach on fort. Fort Anjaneri had less facility of food and water. Value of Physical Attribute as accommodation is very low as 0.2 in tourist place fort Anjaneri, Bhaskargad,

and Alang. The major attribute as transport facility was not good for fort Anjaneri, Mulher, Bhaskargad, and Alang. Tringalgad, and Ramshej fort shows value of parking as 0.4. The values of tourist information and guide of fort Tringalgad and Alang fort are having .04 and Anjaneri and Alang shows 0.2 respectively.

Highest Physical potential value found at fort Ramsej (0.837) followed by Harihar (0.808). It means physical attributes are high developing in this tourist places. These tourist places are well connected with highly urban area like Nasik city. Fort Anjaneri (0.218), Bhaskargad (0.352) and Alang (0.418) shows low potential value of physical attributes. These forts are mainly away from high urban area as well as in less developing taluka.

Conclusion

Potential values for the different forts as tourist place indicate the level of development of attributes. This level affects on the attraction of tourist. Graph (Fig. 2) shows the potential value of social aspects is from 0.3 to 0.766. Highest social potential value is found at fort Harihar (0.776) followed by Ramsej (0.66) and Tringalwadi (0.66). The lowest social potential value found at fort Anjaneri and Alang 0.3 respectively. It shows that the social attribute should develop at fort Anjaneri and Alang. In social as well as physical attribute and fort Harihar and Ramsej shows better condition.

Findings

1. Fort Tringalgad and Anjaneri having less value in social attribute is less than 0.4
2. Fort Bhaskargad having the value 0.5 in Social attribute.
3. Fort Anjaneri found the value of physical attribute is .0218 is lowest.

4. Fort Bhaskargad and Alang shows the value of physical attribute is less than 0.5.
5. Fort Mulher having value of physical attribute is 0.523.

Suggestion

1. New planning strategies needs to be introduced to for increased tourist participation. Social Attribute should develop in Fort Tringalgad and Anjaneri.
2. Historical education awareness must be increased through government and NGO's which will help to develop tourist place as fort Bhaskargad and Alang.
3. MTDC and PWD department should Build New road to fort Bhaskargad and Accommodation or hotels near the fort Harihar, Tringalgad and Bhaskargad.
4. Industrialist should provide Ropeway for fort Harihar and Mulher which will increase the number of tourist.
5. Physical as well as social attribute highly development in Anjaneri, Bhaskargad and Alang.
6. Government should introduce some new guides which will provide best and reliable information about forts.
7. Government has to encourage to NGO, School, colleges, government officers to visit to forts.

Such study has potential to attract experts from the field of planning, economics, artists, architecture and administration in order to all-round development of study region. So that socio-economic status of population may be considerably upgraded in study region.

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